

IMPLEMENTATION OF ASSESSMENT FOR EDUCATIONAL SERVICES FOR MODERATE INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY CHILDREN CLASS 1 AT SLB C BUDAYA BANGSA BANDUNG AND SKh NEGERI 01 CILEGON

TETI RATNAWULAN ¹, LINNA YULIANI ², AINI FARAH ³, DEWI RINI SISWANTI ⁴
and AHMAD HAER ⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5} Universitas Islam Nusantara, Bandung, Indonesia.

E-mail: ¹tetiratnawulan@uinus.ac.id, ²linnayuliani@uinus.ac.id, ³ainifarah@uinus.ac.id,

⁴dewirini@uinus.ac.id, ⁵ahmadhaer@uinus.ac.id

Abstract

The implementation of assessment is an activity to collect various accurate information about the strengths, difficulties and weaknesses of children in certain fields that will be used as a basis for preparing an education program that suits their needs. Intellectual disability children are children who have IQ significantly below the average accompanied by their inability to adapt to the environment. SLB C Budaya Bangsa Bandung and SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon are schools that organize educational services for children with disabilities. This study aims to describe the implementation of assessments for educational services for children with intellectual disabilities at SLB C Budaya Bangsa Bandung and Skh Negeri 01 Cilegon. This research uses descriptive research. The subject of this research is the assessment team at SLB C Budaya Bangsa Bandung and Skh Negeri 01 Cilegon. The data collection techniques used are interviews, observations and documentation studies. In the implementation of the assessment can be divided into 3 stages, preparation, implementation and follow-up, in the preparation stage the teacher compiles the assessment test instrument, prepares the officers, time and place as well as the methods and media/tools that will be used. In the implementation stage, assessment activities include initial activities, preparing for the implementation process, core activities, namely carrying out assessments and final activities of evaluation, calming children, and describing the results, while in the third stage, namely recommending results, informing the results to the principal and parents and making programs. Difficulties experienced were lack of reference books, media/tools, conditioning children and communicating results to parents. Efforts made by finding and completing assessment instruments, giving rewards to children so that children are comfortable, and providing an understanding to parents about the results of the assessment so that children can get the right program. Recommendations are addressed to teachers so that the implementation of assessments is carried out in order to design learning programs according to the abilities and needs of Intellectual disability children

Keywords: Implementation, Assessment, Education Services, Children with Disabilities.

INTRODUCTION

Children with special needs are children who have abnormalities or deviations from the average condition of children in general in terms of physical, mental and social behavior characteristics. The diverse characteristics of children with special needs give rise to abilities that are different from children in general. IDEA 2004 in James (2008:5) formulates several categories of children with special needs who should receive special education and related services. Some of these categories are children who experience: "1) emotional disorders; 2)

mental retardation; 3) multiple disorders; 4) deaf-blindness; 5) dementia; 6) health problems; 7) *orthopedic requirements* (children who experience muscle and bone disorders and need tools to activate other functions in the body); 8) brain injury; 9) language disorders; 10) hearing impairment; and 11) visual impairment".

One category of children with special needs is children with intellectual disability. According to Kustawan in Fatimah (2017: 220) "Intellectual disability is a child who has significant intelligence that is below average and is accompanied by an inability to adapt behavior that appears during development". Furthermore, Rachmayana in Fatimah (2017: 221) argues "Intellectual disability means a condition characterized by a general intelligence function that is below average accompanied by a reduced ability to adapt which begins to arise before the age of 18 years". Still according to Witmer & Kotinsky, Frampton & Gail in Fatimah (2017: 221) as follows:

There are eight needs that are needed by children with disabilities, namely; 1. A feeling of assurance that their needs will be met (*The Sense of Trust*). 2. Feeling authorized to manage themselves (*The Sense of Autonomy*). 3. The feeling of being able to act according to one's own initiative (*The Sense of Initiative*). 4. The feeling of satisfaction in carrying out tasks (*The Sense of Duty and Accomplishment*) 5. The feeling of pride in self-identity (*The Sense of Identity*). 6. Feeling of familiarity (*The Sense of Intimacy*). 7. A sense of parenthood (*The Parental Sense*). 8. The Sense of *Integrity*.

Children with disabilities have the same rights as other children. They need treatment or services to be able to participate optimally in their lives. As stated in the Regulation of the Minister of State for Women's Empowerment and Child Protection No. 10 of 2011 Article 1 (Permeneg PP&PA, 2011) that "handling children with special needs is all activities to ensure and protect children and the rights of children with special needs in order to live, grow, develop and participate optimally in accordance with the dignity of humanity". In this case, one of the services that can be provided to meet the needs of children with disabilities is education services.

The fulfilled needs of educational services for children with disabilities are expected to achieve an independent life so that children with disabilities can participate optimally in accordance with human dignity. McLoughlin (2003) in Haryanto (2012: 17) explains that "assessment in the education of children with special needs or special education is a systematic process using relevant instruments to determine children's learning behavior for placement and learning purposes".

Assessment activities determine the success in providing educational service programs for children with disabilities. Mastery of assessment skills is a professional demand that must be owned by a teacher. Teachers need to master the insights and skills to provide appropriate and correct educational services for children with disabilities. Hermanto (2010:23) explains "The implementation of assessment activities requires adequate skills so that the assessments carried out are right on target and reveal the needs of children with disabilities in depth and breadth, therefore in conducting assessments requires accuracy or thoroughness, especially in

integrating the results of recommendation notes from various experts regarding children with special needs".

Based on the above opinions, researchers can conclude that the implementation of assessment is an activity to collect various accurate information about the strengths, difficulties and weaknesses of children in certain fields which will be used as a basis for preparing an education program that suits their needs.

The results of preliminary studies conducted by researchers in October 2023 at SLB C Budaya Bangsa Bandung and SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon, found problems, namely: The condition of children with intellectual disabilities who are still not ready for the assessment, and parents are not cooperative in providing initial information about the condition and basic abilities of the children. In addition, the understanding of assessment procedures has not been mastered by new teachers, and the implementation of assessments for education services for children with disabilities at SLB C Budaya Bangsa Bandung and SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon is not yet known in detail.

Based on the preliminary study above, the researcher is interested in taking the title "Implementation of Assessments for Education Services for Children with Intellectual Disability at SLB C Budaya Bangsa Bandung and at SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon".

Research conducted by Widiastuti & Winaya (2019: 7) states that "Intellectual disability children have academic obstacles that are such that in their learning services require curriculum modifications that are in accordance with their special needs", in line with research conducted by Abidin (2018: 11) the inhibiting factors faced by teachers in carrying out assessments, and some of these obstacles indirectly have an impact on child development, including not creating good cooperation communication between parents and teachers.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research methods used in this study are as follows:

1. Research Methods

In this study, the type of research used is descriptive research with a qualitative approach. "Research is a process of collecting and analyzing data that is carried out systematically and logically to achieve certain goals" Sukmadinata, (2015: 5). The reason for qualitative research can reveal the symptoms that accompany the problem in detail and what it is, every view, belief, understanding, and behavior formation. "Descriptive research is a type of research that seeks to describe and interpret objects according to what they are" Best, in Darmadi, (2011: 145).

Descriptive research is used to reveal the process of implementing assessments for educational services for children with disabilities at SLB C Budaya Bangsa Bandung and SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon. This research aims to provide descriptive data which is done by collecting data from various sources regarding the implementation of assessments for educational services for children with disabilities. Through the use of descriptive methods, it is hoped that

the data obtained will be more complete, credible and meaningful so that the research objectives can be achieved.

2. Qualitative Approach

Researchers use a qualitative research approach, which is a research method based on the philosophy of post positivism or enterpretatif, used to examine natural object conditions, where researchers are key instruments. According to Moleong (2007: 6) states that, Qualitative research is research that intends to understand the phenomenon of what is experienced by the research subject, for example behavior, perception, motivation, action, etc., holistically, and by means of description in the form of words and language, in a special natural context and by utilizing various scientific methods.

Based on the above opinion, it can be concluded that a qualitative approach is a research that describes or explains a phenomenon or event that has occurred. Therefore, this qualitative research approach was chosen because this research seeks to examine social phenomena in an atmosphere that takes place naturally or naturally.

3. Data Collection Technique

Data collection techniques are the methods used to collect the necessary data. According to Sugiyono (2013:308) that "data collection techniques are the most important step in research, because the purpose of research is to collect data". In this study, the techniques used in collecting data were interviews, observation and documentation.

a. Interview

An interview is a meeting of two individuals exchanging information and thoughts with questions and answers, which is one way to collect data or information. Interviews can also be said to be conversations conducted face-to-face, where the questioner asks directly to the person to be interviewed, in order to get information or data to be obtained. According to Moleong, (2007: 186) "Interviews are used by asking questions directly to sources or informants regarding topics that are the object of research".

Based on the above opinion, the researcher concludes that interviews are question and answer activities that produce information directly. In this study, researchers used *in-depth interviews*. Interviews in this study were conducted with the assessment team which included homeroom teachers, student affairs teachers and curriculum teachers.

b. Observation

Observation is data collection carried out through an observation, accompanied by notes on the condition or behavior of the research subject.

According to Sugiyono (2018: 229) "observation is a data collection technique that has specific characteristics when compared to other techniques" while according to Patton in Poerwandari, (2013: 125) asserts that "observation is an essential data collection method in qualitative research. In order for the data to be accurate and useful, observation must be carried out by researchers who have gone through adequate training, and have made careful and complete

preparations ". It can be concluded that observation techniques are essential data collection methods and have specific characteristics in qualitative research. This observation is also carried out directly, namely how to collect data by using the eye without the help of other standard tools for this purpose. Researchers collect data from classroom observations during learning activities.

c. *Documentation Study*

Documentation is evidence of events that have passed (occurred). The documentation itself can be in the form of writings, drawings or photographs. According to Sanjaya in Risa, (2015: 35) states "Documentation as a way of collecting data obtained from existing documents or stored records, be it in the form of transcripts, books, newspapers, and so on", while according to Awangga (2007: 135) "Documentation is the creation and storage of evidence in research, such as pictures, writings, sounds, and so on for everything, both objects or events that occur". Based on the above opinions, researchers can conclude that documentation is a way of collecting information or events that have occurred in the form of pictures, writings or sounds.

In this study, documents were collected in the form of archives related to the implementation of the assessment, namely the assessment team structure sheet, the flow of the assessment implementation, the assessment instruments used, the assessment profile, the Individual Learning Program (IEP), the registration form sheet and the description of the child's initial abilities, as well as examples of medical diagnoses.

4. Research Instruments

In qualitative research, researchers can act as research instruments. Moleong (2008: 168-172) describes the researcher as an instrument that has the following characteristics: "1) Responsive, 2) Can adjust, 3) Emphasize wholeness, 4) Based on self-knowledge, 5) Process data as soon as possible, 6) Use opportunities to clarify, 7) Utilize opportunities to find unusual respondents".

In this research, the researcher is the key instrument who goes directly to the field to explore and collect various data and information needed.

5. Data Analysis Technique

Analysis is used in qualitative research and is more focused on the research process while in the field along with data collection. The implementation of the data collection process consists of three components that are interrelated and carried out repeatedly. The following are the steps of analysis in qualitative research:

a. *Data reduction*

According to Sugiyono, (2018: 247-249) "Data reduction is summarizing, selecting key things, focusing on important things that are in accordance with the research topic, looking for themes and patterns, ultimately providing a clearer picture and making it easier to do further data collection".

b. *Data presentation (data display)*

According to Sugiyono, (2014: 341) "in qualitative research, data presentation can be done in the form of brief descriptions, charts, and relationships between categories". Presentation of data is a description of detailed conditions to tell and answer each problem in the study.

c. *Conclusion drawing/verification*

Conclusion drawing/verification is the activity of concluding or verifying. Conclusions were drawn since the beginning of the data and verified during the research and then developed with data that had been collected through interview data, observation, and documentation. An interactive process was carried out to compare interview data with observation data. This effort was made to strengthen the conclusion and validity of the data, then carried out between the components of the analysis, which includes data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Results

Activities Carried Out By Teachers in Carrying Out Assessments for Education Services for Grade 1 Children at Slb C Budaya Bangsa Bandung and SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon.

a. Preparation for Assessment Implementation

1) Test Type

Oral, performance and observation (adjusted to the assessment instrument used and what aspects are to be measured or assessed).

2) Officer

Consists of 3 teachers consisting of the Assessment Coordinator (as the person in charge of the entire series of assessment activities), Deputy Head of Student Affairs (as the one who will determine the placement of children with moderate deafness in which class according to the child's abilities and needs based on the assessment results, Deputy Head of Curriculum (who will recommend suitable learning for moderate deafness children based on their abilities and needs based on the assessment results).

3) Time Allocation

Aimed at new children who enter at the beginning of the school year, the assessment is carried out during the PPDB timeframe before the start of the effective school day.

4) Place of Assessment

Held in the hall of SLB C Budaya Bangsa because there is no assessment room while in SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon the implementation of the assessment is in the assessment room.

5) Methods and Media

The methods used are direct tests on children with moderate deformities (Written tests, oral tests and performance tests), interviews conducted with parents. The media used is adjusted to the assessment instrument that has been prepared and used during the assessment.

b. Assessment Implementation

1) Initial Activity:

At the beginning of the assessment activities in the two schools is conditioning the child to enter the room that has been prepared complete with the media that will be used during the implementation of the assessment activities. The child is conditioned to enter the room without being accompanied by parents, the aim is to avoid intervention from parents during the assessment process.

2) Core Activities

In the core activities at SLB C Budaya Bangsa and at SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon conduct oral test assessments in the form of simple questions to find out the extent of children's language and communication development. In addition, the two schools also conduct written and performance tests such as giving questions in the form of thickening words, adding pictures, equating colors and others to measure children's cognitive abilities while to find out children's motor skills at SLB C Budaya Bangsa gives questions in the form of cutting and pasting similar pictures also done at SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon but at SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon also adds questions in the form of equating pictures.

3) End/Closing Activity

- (a) In the final activity, the teacher calms the children down and gives *rewards* as a form of appreciation for the efforts that have been made.
- (b) Describe the results, after finishing with the entire assessment process that has been carried out, the teacher then describes the results of the assessment that has been carried out and the results of the portfolio / work.
- (c) Analyzing results, Based on the data that has been collected in the initial activities, the data is then analyzed so that temporary conclusions are obtained as an initial description of the actual and factual conditions of the children.

c. Follow-up

1) Make recommendations

After analyzing the results of the assessment, the teacher then makes recommendations on the results of the assessment submitted to related parties, namely to the principal and therapist.

2) Informing the result

Respondents also informed the school principal of the results of the assessment so that additional supportive opinions could be obtained, and the child's parents so that they were

aware of their son/daughter's abilities. Difficulties experienced in carrying out assessments of education services for grade 1 mild Intellectual disability children at SLB C Budaya Bangsa Bandung and SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon

- a. The difficulties experienced by both schools during preparation were in formulating assessment instruments, the lack of props/media and the unavailability of a special assessment room at SLB C Budaya Bangsa.
- b. Difficulties experienced during the implementation of assessments in these two schools conditioned children who often did not want to participate in assessment activities because they felt uncomfortable with new people, and there were several children who were non-verbal so that the implementation of oral tests was not achieved.
- c. Difficulties during follow-up include parents' lack of understanding of the assessment results and many parents who do not care about the assessment results.

Efforts made by teachers to overcome the difficulties experienced in carrying out assessments of education services for grade 1 mild Intellectual disability children at SLB C Budaya Bangsa Bandung and SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon.

- a. The efforts made by both schools during the preparation were trying to find reference books on assessment instruments, and asking the school to prepare/provide a special room for assessment.
- b. Efforts made during the implementation of the assessment are to give something or things that children like as a lighter so that children can be more comfortable with new people and for non-verbal children the teacher gives written and performance tests.
- c. Efforts made by both schools at the time of follow-up were to provide understanding and communicate to parents about the factual condition of the child and provide knowledge about what things should be done.

2. Discussion

Assessment is an activity that must be done. This statement was emphasized by the coordinator of the assessment team and the principal of SLB C Budaya Bangsa, who explained that the importance of assessment is to find out and explore the basic abilities of children with disabilities to then be used as a basis for making learning programs and class placements that suit the needs of children with disabilities. Meanwhile, according to the coordinator of the assessment team and the principal of SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon, the assessment is to see the strengths and weaknesses of children with disabilities. After knowing this, it can be known the needs of children with Intellectual disability to be given therapy or programs that suit their needs.

Based on the results of the research, the purpose of the implementation of assessments at SLB C Budaya Bangsa Bandung and SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon is to find out and explore more deeply the strengths and weaknesses of children with disabilities and the potential that the children still have. After knowing the needs of the child, the program and educational

placement can be determined according to the child's condition. This is in accordance with the statement of the *National Information Center for Children and Youth Disabilities* (Pierangelo & Giuliani, 2013: 6) which explains that the assessment process aims to obtain information about the abilities of children, the obstacles faced by children, determine programs that suit the needs of children, determine individualized learning programs, and determine children's education programs.

Based on the results of the study, it was found that in the stage of preparing the assessment, the first step taken was to compile the assessment test instrument, assessment officers, time and place allocations, and prepare assessment methods and media. During the implementation of the assessment the teacher conditions the children and the media to be used, gives oral tests, written tests and performance for non-verbal children and gives *rewards* to children after completing the assessment. After the assessment is carried out the teacher carries out activities to analyze the results and compile recommendations given to the principal and parents. The difficulties experienced by teachers during the assessment are when preparing assessment instruments, conditioning children in the room, and there are still parents who do not understand the results of the assessment. Teachers try to overcome difficulties during the implementation of the assessment by looking for reference books, giving something that children like so that children are comfortable with new people, selecting media/tools that are in accordance with the assessment instrument so that what will be measured can be achieved, and teachers continue to provide understanding to parents so that parents care more about the results of the assessment so that children can get the right learning program according to the assessment results.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Conclusions

a. General Conclusions

- 1) Activities carried out by teachers in the implementation of assessments include several aspects of abilities that are assessed, namely: language and communication interaction, motor skills, and pre-academic abilities. Follow-up on the results of the assessment carried out by the teacher includes: compiling an assessment profile, conducting internal discussions to discuss the results of the assessment, and developing a program.
- 2) The difficulties experienced by teachers during the assessment are when preparing assessment instruments, conditioning children in the room, and there are still parents who do not understand the results of the assessment.
- 3) Efforts made are by looking for reference books, providing something that children like so that children are comfortable with new people, selecting media/tools that are in accordance with the assessment instrument so that what will be measured can be achieved, and teachers continue to provide understanding to parents to be more concerned with the results of the assessment so that children can get the right learning program according to the results of the assessment.

b. Specific conclusions

Based on the results of the research and discussion, it can be concluded that the implementation of assessments at SLB C Budaya Bangsa Bandung and at SKh Negeri 01 Cilegon is divided into three stages, namely: preparation of assessment implementation, implementation of assessment data collection, and follow-up of assessment results. Preparation for the implementation of the assessment includes: coordinating with parents of children with disabilities, preparing assessment instruments that will be used. Assessment data collection is carried out by the assessment team through interviews, documentation, treatment, and observation methods.

2. Recommendation

Based on the above conclusions regarding the results of the study, the researcher intends to provide input with the aim of being used as a reference and more perfect development with recommendations, among others:

a. For children with disabilities

It is expected to get a very rigid assessment with the results of this study, then the results of the assessment become an evaluation material for each child so that they can develop according to different achievements and needs.

b. For Teachers

Can play a more active role in the implementation of assessment activities for education services for children with disabilities, such as providing subjective assessments according to the conditions that exist in each child in order to understand the needs of children with disabilities properly.

c. For Schools

The implementation of assessment activities for education services for children with disabilities is good enough, but the implementation is expected to be further improved, can be done continuously in order to get maximum assessment results.

d. For Researchers

Can make an illustration in adding references in making research and can be an illustration in carrying out assessments in the school where teaching.

References

- 1) Cohen, Libby G & Spenciner, Lorraine J. (2013). *Assessment of Children and Youth with Special Needs. Fourth Edition*. USA: Pearson Prentice Hall
- 2) Darmadi, Hamid.(2011). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan*. Bandung: Penerbit Alfabeta.
- 3) Hallahan, Daniel P, Kauffman, James M. & Pullen, Paige C. (2009). *Exceptional Learners: An Introduction to Special Education*. United States of America: Pearson.

- 4) Haryanto.(2012). *Identifikasi dan Asesmen Pendidikan Anak Berkebutuhan Khusus*.Kementrian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan.
- 5) James, Ami. (2008). *School Success for Children with Special Needs: Everything You Need to Know to Help Your Child Learn*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- 6) Kopendium Indonesia.(2010). *Perjanjian, Hukum dan Peraturan Menjamin Semua Anak Memperoleh Kesamaan Hak Untuk Kualitas Pendidikan Dalam Cara Inklusif. Edisi Keempat*. Diakses dari http://www.idp-europe.org/docs/Compendium_Indonesia_indonesia_4.pdf pada tanggal 09 Mei 2023 pukul 08.54 WIB.
- 7) Moleong, Lexy J. (2007). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: PT Teen.
- 8) Mumpuniarti, dkk.(2014). *Peningkatan Ketrampilan Asesmen Anak Berkebutuhan Khusus untuk Guru Sekolah Luar Biasa. Laporan Program Pengabdian Pada Masyarakat*. Fakultas Ilmu Pendidikan.Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta.
- 9) Pierangelo, Roger & Guiliani, George A. (2013). *Assessment in Special Education: a Practical Approach*. 4th Edition. Singapore: Pearson Education South Asia.
- 10) Rashid, Naila.(2012). *Assessment of Stress and Coping of Parents of Disabled Children: Parental Stress and Coping of Children with Disabilities*. Germany: LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing.
- 11) Sukmadinata, Nana Syaodih.(2015). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- 12) Sugiyono (2013). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan: Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 13) Sunardi, Tjutju & Sunaryo.(2007). *Intervensi Anak Berkebutuhan Khusus*. Jakarta: Departemen Pendidikan Nasional.
- 14) Soendari, Tjutju.(2009). *Asesmen sebagai Dasar Penyusunan Program Intervensi Anak Berkebutuhan Khusus*. Makalah. Diakses dari
- 15) http://file.upi.edu/Direktori/Fip/Jur._Pendid._Luar_Biasa/195602141980032/Tjutju_Soendari/Makalah/Asesmen__makalah_.pdf pada tanggal 09 Mei 2023 11.50 WIB.
- 16) Triani, Nani (2012). *Panduan Asesmen Anak Berkebutuhan Khusus*. Jakarta: PT Luxima Metro Media.